

EFFECT OF YOGIC PRACTICES ON BODY COMPOSITION AMONG COLLEGE WOMEN

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Abstract:

In this context, the investigator made an attempt to investigate the effect of yogic practices on body composition among college women. To achieve the purpose of the study, thirty women were randomly selected as subjects from A.V.V.M. Sri Pushpam College, Poondi, Thanjavur. The age of the subjects were ranged from 18 to 21 years. The subjects selected for this study were divided into two groups of fifteen subjects each. The experimental group I underwent yoga training and group II acted as a control group. The subjects were exposed to a yoga training programme for six weeks. The training programmes were organized in a progressive manner. The obtained data from the experimental and control groups initial and final readings were statistically analyzed with analysis of covariance (ANCOVA). The level of confidence which was fixed at 0.05 levels was considered as an appropriate one for this study. It was observed that the six weeks of yoga training have significantly reduced the body composition.

Key Words: Yogic Practices, Body Composition

Introduction:

The yogic art is cosmic art. When you achieve Yoga, you find pure consciousness in action and good health, resistance power, etc. When the heart works normally through the circulation of blood, it gets the blood purified by the lungs and keeps the digestive system in order; the various glands function and maintain the balance of body; and the mind works calmly and keeps the body functioning through the intricate nervous system. In case of illness it does become inevitable to resort to medication, but health is regained only through the intrinsic strength of the inner organs. Medicine helps when the body mechanism functions properly. Many of the common health and social problems cannot be solved through germ theories, antibiotics, vaccines or surgeries. The fascinating diagnostic tools have started pointing to the role of mind on matter. Biochemical, psychological, neuro-physiological and immunological researchers are recognizing the role of lifestyle, stress, suppressed emotions and so on as the cause of many of the challenges faced today. Hence health professionals are forced to accept the paradigm shift in the approach of understanding human health problems. As everyone knows, yoga involves different patterns of exercises and postures, practicing them appropriately help to improve muscle strength, stamina, immune stability, perceptual sharpness, intelligence, memory, emotional stability and altogether maintain a positive physical and mental health (Kristal et al. 2005).

Methodology:

In this context, the investigator made an attempt to investigate the effect of yogic practices on body composition among college women. To achieve the purpose of the study, thirty women were randomly selected as subjects from A.V.V.M. Sri Pushpam College, Poondi, Thanjavur. The age of the subjects were ranged from 18 to 21 years. The subjects selected for this study were divided into two groups of fifteen subjects each. The experimental group I underwent yoga training and group II acted as a control group. The subjects were exposed to a yoga training programme for six weeks. The training programmes were organized in a progressive manner. The obtained data from the experimental and control groups initial and final readings were statistically analyzed with analysis of covariance (ANCOVA). The level of confidence which was fixed at 0.05 levels was considered as an appropriate one for this study.

Results:

Table 1: Computation of Mean and Analysis of Covariance of Body Composition of Experimental and Control Groups

	Experimental Group	Control Group	Source of variance	Sum of squares	DF	Mean square	F
Pre Test Mean	30.32	30.71	BG	1.16	1	1.16	0.36
			WG	89.88	28	3.21	
Post Test Mean	29.10	30.56	BG	15.98	1	15.98	7.33*
			WG	61.12	28	2.18	
Adjusted Post Mean	29.20	30.46	BG	11.78	1	11.78	8.35*
			WG	38.30	27	1.41	

* Significant at 0.05 level

The above table indicates the adjusted mean value of body composition of experimental and control groups were 29.20 and 30.46 respectively. The obtained F-ratio of 8.35 for adjusted mean was greater than the table value 4.21 for the degrees of freedom 1 and 27 required for significance at 0.05 level of confidence. The result of the study indicates that there was a significant difference among experimental and control groups on body composition. The above table also indicates that both pre and post test means of experimental and control groups also differ significantly. The pre and post mean values of body composition of both control and experimental groups are graphically represented in the Figure 1.

Figure 1

Conclusion:

It was observed that the six weeks of yoga training have significantly reduced the body composition.

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